

ECONOMIC MANAGEMENT MECHANISM OF INNOVATION PROCESSES IN INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: This article presents concepts and theoretical analyzes of the management system of scientific and technological development of industrial enterprises. In addition, the relevance of conceptual, theoretical and practical researches and innovative processes, views on the management of scientific and technical development depends on many reasons.

Keywords: Industrial enterprises, small business, innovative economy, economic growth, economic factors, conceptual, theories.

Econometric modeling to improve the mechanism of economic management of innovative processes in industrial enterprises means the combined study of scientific and analytical methods of economic analysis and decision-making through these models. When innovations are organized and managed, learning and studying their economic impact will help to increase the capacity of industrial enterprises to develop and improve their strategies. Some of the key processes involved in this modeling are:

Data collection and analysis: Data collection related to innovation processes, important for an industrial enterprise or sector. Before building models for the education of economy and innovative activity, it is necessary to collect and analyze data.

The economic potential of the region is the ability of the branches of the regional economic complexes to produce industrial and agricultural products, implement capital construction, transport goods and provide services to the population in a certain period. Economic potential is determined by a system of interrelated indicators that describe in detail the economic and social spheres of the region. The potential of production resources - it has a value in concrete monetary terms and is manifested in real forms of various elements of production capital in the form of fixed and circulating capital, circulating funds and circulating funds. The most important is the indicator of the main funds of enterprises, which describes the general potential of the region.

To increase the efficiency and competitiveness of the industry on the basis of innovative development of industrial sectors of our country, growth of their export potential, technical and technological arming of production enterprises, supply of the domestic market with products produced by national enterprises, effective use of existing resources, implementation of an active investment policy increase can be achieved. The formation of the innovative potential of regional industrial enterprises will depend on the complex system of interrelationships of factors and conditions that accelerate innovation processes. This situation accelerates processes such as scientific research and experimental design development, application of innovative technologies of the product. The concept of "innovative potential" began to actively enter science from the late 70s of the 20th century. It was clarified and developed in methodological and theoretical studies of a number of

scientists. However, until today, a universally accepted definition of this concept has not been developed.

When analyzing the theoretical and scientific approaches to the formation of innovative management, D. Nort's "Theory of Institutional Changes" is based on the institutional norms, rules, laws and activities of the regional innovation system (HIT). can be understood in relation to In harmony with institutions-organizations, they form an institutional environment.

❖ that the system of support and encouragement of young scientists is not developed and does not exist in some regions;

❖ that the system of financing scientific research and technological development is not well developed;

❖ lack of full implementation of the legal framework for the protection of small enterprises in the industrial sector.

In order to eliminate these problems, to support the innovative enterprises that are being formed in the region, it is proposed to form innovative infrastructures to ensure the interaction of innovative participants in the regions.

Today, foreign scientists distinguish the following factors that determine the competitiveness of the region:

- the quality of the labor force (level of education and qualification), a developed labor market that allows workers of the given category to find work;

- existence of research centers that allow creation of new technologies and ITTKI, exchange of information;

- favorable business environment (low tax rates and availability of financial support from the local government, creation of business service facilities, advance knowledge of the actions of the local administration and its high-quality management of the territory);

Development of a set of special measures in investment, industry, finance and credit spheres aimed at activating internal sources of economic growth and including their economic complexes in the unified state economic policy in relation to regions that are difficult to adapt to market relations due to objective reasons. need

CIS countries have many similarities in regional issues not only with developed countries, but also with developing countries that have achieved a high level of economic development and maintained the dynamism of socio-economic restructuring in the region.

As part of the restructuring of the economy management system in the republic and the creation of an institutional base for the implementation of deep market changes, the following was implemented:

- gradual transition from directive planning to indicative regulation;

- as a result of the reforms carried out in management structures, independent economic subjects - concerns and associations were created instead of narrow ministries and institutions;

- basic market infrastructures - banking system, commodity and stock exchanges, labor exchange, state institutions supporting small and private entrepreneurship were formed;

- gradual liberalization of the price and the market, including foreign trade, was carried out.

Study of innovative activities: Through econometric modeling analysis, a model can be constructed to study how innovative activities can increase the time and effort of an industrial enterprise.

Evaluating innovation and making it more rigorous: There are a number of criteria and indicators for more rigorous evaluation of innovation. By running models, it is used to study how innovation can ensure the achievement of the state.

Organization of financial means and resources: It is also important to construct models to study the provision of innovative processes by the organization of financial means and resources. It helps to optimize costs in the management of innovation projects and to determine the economically correct course of innovation application.

Reinforcement and management analysis: Used to study how innovation activities develop and reinforce management by running models and managing results. Econometric modeling helps in economic analysis of innovative processes of industrial enterprises, development of strategies and efficiency of economic management mechanisms. These models should be created on the basis of available data and analysis, and its results will show what steps the enterprise should take in the development of innovative activities.

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